

2nd analysis of ellipse equation:

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Abstract:

The general equations of an ellipse are typically utilized in various fields, such as computer graphics, space research, and other areas of scientific inquiry. This paper presents a simplified form of certain general equations for an ellipse, designed to facilitate the easy determination of points during the construction of an elliptical figure.

Summary:

The various forms of the equation of an ellipse are governed by specific rules; each type of equation is distinct—for instance, this variation is determined by whether the ellipse is situated along the x-axis, along the y-axis, to the right of the y-axis, or to the left of the x-axis. It is through these diverse mathematical expressions that the equation of an ellipse can be formulated.

In the present research paper, an attempt has been made to devise a novel form of the elliptical equation, which would enable the determination of the general equation of an ellipse by first identifying its focal points.

Previously, most of the work was carried out in the paper titled "[General Equation of an Ellipse](#)" and in this paper, it has been further generalized.

If the general equation of an ellipse is $mx^2 + ny^2 + oxy + px + qy + r = 0$, then the equation can be written as

$$y = (sx + t) \pm \sqrt{ux^2 - vx + w}$$

The method for determining the values of s, t, u, v and w is discussed here.

Proof:

Certain general matters have been proven and assumed in advance.

1. An ellipse has two focal points.
2. The sum of the distances from the foci to any point (on the ellipse) is constant.

$$|f_1P| + |f_2P| = k$$

3. If p, f₁, f₂ are collinear

$$2|f_1P| + |f_1f_2| = k \text{ or, } |PB| = k$$

And we can generally say that, [\[From General equation of Ellipse v1\]¹](#)

If f₁(x₂,y₂), f₂(x₃,y₃) and P(x₁,y₁)

$$a = (x_2 - x_3), \quad b = (y_2 - y_3)$$

$$a_1 = (x_2 + x_3), \quad b_1 = (y_2 + y_3)$$

$$c = (x_2^2 + y_2^2), \quad d = (x_3^2 + y_3^2)$$

$$k = 2|(x_1, y_1)(x_2, y_2)| + |(x_2, y_2)(x_3, y_3)|$$

$$m = (k^2 - a^2), \quad n = (k^2 - b^2), o = -2ab$$

$$p = (a(c - d) - k^2a_1)$$

$$q = (b(c - d) - k^2b_1)$$

$$r = cd - \left(\frac{c + d - k^2}{2}\right)^2$$

Therefore, the general equation of the ellipse is $mx^2 + ny^2 + oxy + px + qy + r = 0$

$$\text{Or, } ny^2 + (ox + q)y + (mx^2 + px + r) = 0$$

Again, according to the Sridhar Acharya's Formula ^[2], $y = \frac{-(ox+q) \pm \sqrt{(ox+q)^2 - 4n(mx^2+px+r)}}{2n}$

$$\text{Or, } y = -\left(\frac{ox+q}{2n}\right) \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{ox+q}{2n}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{mx^2+px+r}{n}\right)}$$

now generalize this equation more,

$-\left(\frac{ox+q}{2n}\right)$ this part can be represented as $(sx + t)$ and

$\sqrt{\left(\frac{ox+q}{2n}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{mx^2+px+r}{n}\right)}$ this part can be represented as $\sqrt{ux^2 - vx + w}$

So, the equation can be written as $y = (sx + t) \pm \sqrt{ux^2 - vx + w}$

Where $s = \frac{ab}{n}$, $t = \frac{1}{2}(b_1 - sa_1)$, $u = s^2 - \frac{m}{n}$, $v = ua_1$, $w = t^2 - \frac{r}{n}$

Conclusion:

From the proof, it is evident that we can derive the general equation of an ellipse from its two focal points, and express it in the form $y = f(x)$.

If we have two focal points $f_1(x_2, y_2)$, $f_2(x_3, y_3)$

Then the general equation of an ellipse $y = (sx + t) \pm \sqrt{ux^2 - vx + w}$

Where, $a = (x_2 - x_3)$, $b = (y_2 - y_3)$, $a_1 = (x_2 + x_3)$, $b_1 = (y_2 + y_3)$, $c = (x_2^2 + y_2^2)$, $d = (x_3^2 + y_3^2)$,
 $m = (k^2 - a^2)$, $n = (k^2 - b^2)$, $k = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} + 2k_a$, $r = cd - \left(\frac{c+d-k^2}{2}\right)^2$, $s = \frac{ab}{n}$, $t = \frac{1}{2}(b_1 - sa_1)$,
 $u = s^2 - \frac{m}{n}$, $v = ua_1$, $w = t^2 - \frac{r}{n}$

$[k_a = |(x_1, y_1)(x_2, y_2)|$ or, $|f_1P|$ see diagram of ellipse]

JS code and output of algorithm:

```
<canvas id="myCanvas" width="500" height="500" style="border:1px solid #000"></canvas>
```

```
<script>
```

```
const canvas = document.getElementById('myCanvas');  
const ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');
```

```
function ellipse(x2, y2, x3, y3, k_a) {  
  let a = x2 - x3;  
  let b = y2 - y3;  
  let a1 = x2 + x3;  
  let b1 = y2 + y3;  
  let c = Math.pow(x2, 2) + Math.pow(y2, 2);  
  let d = Math.pow(x3, 2) + Math.pow(y3, 2);  
  let k = Math.sqrt(Math.pow(a, 2) + Math.pow(b, 2)) + (2 * k_a);  
  let k1 = Math.pow(k, 2);  
  let n = k1 - Math.pow(b, 2);  
  let r = c * d - Math.pow((c + d - k1) / 2, 2);
```

```
  let s = (a * b) / n;  
  let t = -(s * a1) + b1 / 2;  
  let u = Math.pow(s, 2) - ((k1 - Math.pow(a, 2)) / n);  
  let v = u * a1;  
  let w = Math.pow(t, 2) - (r / n);
```

```
  var x_min = (v + Math.sqrt(Math.pow(v, 2) - 4 * u * w)) / (2 * u)  
  var y_min = s * x_min + t  
  var x_max = (v - Math.sqrt(Math.pow(v, 2) - 4 * u * w)) / (2 * u)  
  var y_max = s * x_max + t
```

```
  var y_temp1 = y_min  
  var y_temp2 = y_min
```

```

for (let x = x_min; x <= x_max; x) {
  var temp_x = x + 1;
  var y_w = ((u * Math.pow(x + 1, 2)) - (v * (x + 1)) + w)

  if (y_w > 0) {
    ctx.beginPath();
    ctx.moveTo(x, y_temp1);
    y_temp1 = (s * temp_x + t) - Math.sqrt(y_w)
    ctx.lineTo(x + 1, y_temp1);
    ctx.lineWidth = 1;
    ctx.strokeStyle = "blue";
    ctx.stroke();

    ctx.beginPath();
    ctx.moveTo(x, y_temp2);
    y_temp2 = (s * temp_x + t) + Math.sqrt(y_w)
    ctx.lineTo(x + 1, y_temp2);
    ctx.lineWidth = 1;
    ctx.strokeStyle = "blue";
    ctx.stroke();
  }
  else {
    ctx.beginPath();
    ctx.moveTo(x, y_temp1);
    y_temp1 = y_max
    ctx.lineTo(x, y_temp1);
    ctx.lineWidth = 1;
    ctx.strokeStyle = "blue";
    ctx.stroke();

    ctx.beginPath();
    ctx.moveTo(x, y_temp2);
    y_temp2 = y_max
    ctx.lineTo(x, y_temp2);
    ctx.lineWidth = 1;
    ctx.strokeStyle = "blue";
    ctx.stroke();
  }
  x = x + 1;
}
}

```

```

ellipse(70, 50, 300, 300, 25);

```

```

</script>

```

Output:

References:

- [1] General equation of Ellipse v1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14632548>
- [2] Sridhar Acharya's Formula: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quadratic_formula